

Molar volume, viscosity and conductance studies of sodium bromide in methanol + DMF system

Shashi Kant*, Akashdeep and Vikas Bharti

Department of Chemistry, Himachal Pradesh University, Summer Hill, Shimla-171 005, Himachal Pradesh, India

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Abstract : Molar volume, viscosity and conductance of solutions of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide have been calculated from density, viscosity and conductance data respectively at temperatures 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K. The structure breaker behaviour of sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide solutions is inferred from the sign of $(\partial^2\Phi_v^0/\partial T^2)_P$, dB/dT and temperature coefficient of Walden product i.e. $d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)/dT$ values.

Keywords : Molar volume, viscosity, conductance, sodium bromide, *N,N*-dimethylformamide-methanol system.

Introduction

Thermodynamic and transport studies of electrolytes in aqua organic and mixed organic solvent systems are important and have been carried out by number of workers¹⁻⁶ to observe the nature of solvation of ions on the addition of protic organic solvent to water or to some aprotic solvent. The study of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K temperatures was carried out to understand the nature of solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions by measuring the density, molar volume, molar conductance and viscosity of their solutions.

Experimental

Double distilled water with specific conductance in the range of 0.1×10^{-6} to $1.0 \times 10^{-6} \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$ was used for preparation of the solutions. All the solutions were prepared by weight method and conversions of molality to molarity were done by using the standard expression⁷. Methanol (Glaxo Laboratories, AR grade of 99.5% purity) and *N,N*-dimethylformamide (Sisco Research Laboratories, AR grade of 99.5% purity) were used. Sodium bromide (BDH, AR grade of 99.8% purity) was dried over anhydrous calcium chloride for more than 48 h and used. The density measurements were carried out with

the help of 20 ml pycnometer. An electronic balance with an accuracy of $\pm 1.0 \times 10^{-4}$ g was used for mass determinations. Viscosity was determined with a modified capillary type viscometer⁸. The conductance was measured with the help of calibrated digital conductivity meter (HARCO Ltd.) at 50 Hz. Conductivity cell of cell constant of $0.9680 \pm 0.001 \text{cm}^{-1}$ at 25 °C was used. All measurements were made in an electric water thermostat maintained at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K (variation limit of ± 0.05 °C).

Results and discussion

The apparent molar volume of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide solutions have been calculated from density data (Table 1) by using eq. (1),

$$\Phi_v = \frac{M_2}{d} - \frac{1000(d - d_0)}{m d d_0} \quad (1)$$

where d_0 is the density of solvent, d is the density of solution, m is the molality of solution and M_2 the molecular weight of sodium bromide. Errors in Φ_v were calculated from eq. (2),

$$\Delta\Phi_v = (2\Delta d/d^2)(1000/m + M_2) \quad (2)$$

The error in apparent molar volume as derived from eq.

Table 1. Densities, apparent molar volumes of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in dimethylformamide at different temperatures

Concn. $C \times 10^2$ (mol L ⁻¹)	0.1071 mol% methanol							
	Temp. = 298.15 K $d_0 = 0.9430 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$		Temp. = 303.15 K $d_0 = 0.9408 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$		Temp. = 308.15 K $d_0 = 0.9358 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$		Temp. = 313.15 K $d_0 = 0.9338 \text{ g cm}^{-3}$	
	Density d (g cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume Φ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	Density d (g cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume Φ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	Density d (g cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume Φ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	Density d (g cm ⁻³)	Apparent molar volume Φ_v (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
0.939	0.9427	189.0	0.9405	189.3	0.9354	200.0	0.9332	220.1
1.876	0.9429	163.9	0.9406	169.3	0.9355	175.1	0.9334	180.4
3.745	0.9438	138.8	0.9414	144.2	0.9362	150.1	0.9340	155.5
5.606	0.9453	120.2	0.9429	124.0	0.9377	128.4	0.9354	133.8
7.459	0.9474	103.3	0.9450	106.3	0.9398	109.9	0.9373	116.7
9.305	0.9498	90.0	0.9473	93.6	0.9420	97.8	0.9395	103.3

(2) was estimated to range from $\pm 0.06 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.01 M concentration to $\pm 0.10 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ at 0.12 M concentration. The limiting apparent molar volume is estimated by using Masson's eq.⁹

$$\Phi_v = \Phi_v^0 + S_v \sqrt{C} \quad (3)$$

where Φ_v^0 and S_v are calculated from the intercept and slope of the plots of Φ_v vs \sqrt{C} (Fig. 1). The Φ_v^0 is a measure of solute-solvent interactions¹⁰. The limiting apparent molar volume (Φ_v^0) values for sodium bromide

Fig. 1. Plots of Φ_v vs $C^{1/2}$ for NaBr in 0.1071 mol percent of methanol in DMF at different temperatures.

in different mol percent of methanol in N,N -dimethylformamide increase with increase in concentration of methanol in N,N -dimethylformamide, which shows that

there is increase in solute-solvent interactions. This may be due to more solvation of Na^+ and Br^- ions by the addition of methanol to N,N -dimethylformamide. N,N -Dimethylformamide solvates preferably cation being basic in nature. The Φ_v^0 values for sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in N,N -dimethylformamide increase with rise in temperature and it may be due to decrease in association between solvent molecules with rise in temperature, thus making more free solvent molecules available for solvation of ions and hence solute-solvent interactions increases with rise in temperature.

The values of Φ_v are quite high up to concentration $5 \times 10^{-2} M$ which may be due to more solvation of ions at lower concentration of sodium bromide in binary solvent system (DMF + MeOH). Beyond concentrations $5 \times 10^{-2} M$ the values of Φ_v decrease because of decrease in solvation of ions with increase in concentration of sodium bromide in the binary solvent system (DMF + MeOH). The values of limiting apparent molar volume and slopes S_v are recorded in Table 3. The slope S_v in Masson's equation may be attributed to the measure of ion-ion or solute-solute interactions¹¹⁻¹³, large negative values of S_v for sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in N,N -dimethylformamide account for very weak solute-solute interactions.

The temperature dependence of Φ_v^0 ¹⁴ is given by

$$\Phi_v^0 = a + bT + cT^2 \quad (4)$$

where T is temperature expressed in Kelvin and a , b , c

Table 2. Relative viscosities and molar conductance of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at different temperatures

Concn. $C \times 10^2$ (mol L ⁻¹)	0.1071 mol% methanol							
	Temp. = 298.15 K		Temp. = 303.15 K		Temp. = 308.15 K		Temp. = 313.15 K	
	Relative viscosity η/η_0	Molar cond. Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Relative viscosity η/η_0	Molar cond. Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Relative viscosity η/η_0	Molar cond. Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Relative viscosity η/η_0	Molar cond. Λ_m ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)
0.939	1.037	76.25	1.003	83.04	1.004	80.71	1.051	82.64
1.876	1.042	72.75	1.009	79.44	1.012	77.62	1.059	78.82
3.745	1.052	68.13	1.022	74.80	1.027	73.45	1.078	75.46
5.606	1.065	65.00	1.036	71.46	1.043	70.00	1.099	72.11
7.459	1.076	61.88	1.049	68.88	1.060	67.26	1.117	69.21
9.305	1.087	59.38	1.062	65.92	1.073	65.00	1.137	66.90

are constants¹⁴. For sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide the values of Φ_V^0 were determined at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15, 313.15 K and using those values a , b , c were calculated using eq. (4). So for sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide, the expression becomes as,

$$\Phi_V^0 = 165.1 + 3.1405T - 0.0295T^2 \quad (5)$$

The limiting apparent molar expansibility, $\Phi_E^0 = (\partial\Phi_V^0/\partial T)_P$ was calculated for sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide from eq. (5) is given in Table 3. The values of Φ_E^0 increase with increase in temperature for sodium bromide in 0.1070

mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide, which indicates the presence of "caging effect"¹⁵.

The structure making/breaking capacity of sodium bromide may be interpreted with the help of Hepler's reasoning¹⁶; on the basis of sign of $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P$. It has been shown from general thermodynamic eq. (6),

$$\overline{(\partial C_P^0/\partial P)}_T = -T(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P \quad (6)$$

where C_P^0 is the partial molar heat capacity at infinite dilution. For sodium bromide the sign of $(\partial^2\Phi_V^0/\partial T^2)_P$ has been found to be negative in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide. It suggests that sodium bromide acts as structure breaker in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Viscosity studies :

The viscosity data (Table 2) has been analyzed on the basis of Jones-Dole equation¹⁷,

$$\eta_s/\eta_0 = 1 + A\sqrt{C} + BC \quad (7)$$

where η_s and η_0 are viscosities of solution and solvent respectively, C is the molar concentration and A , B are constants. The values of A and B have been determined from the intercept and slope of linear plots of $(\eta_s/\eta_0 - 1)/\sqrt{C}$ versus \sqrt{C} . The values of A and B of different solutions are recorded in Table 4.

Parameter A of Jones-Dole equation represents the contribution from solute-solute interactions¹⁸. The values of A for sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide are very low which suggest very weak solute-solute interactions.

Table 3. Limiting apparent molar volume Φ_V^0 , S_V and apparent molar expansibility (Φ_E^0) of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at different temperatures

System	Temp. (T) (K)	Φ_V^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)	S_V (cm ³ L ^{1/2} mol ^{-3/2})	Φ_E^0 (cm ³ mol ⁻¹)
(MeOH + DMF)				
mol% of MeOH				
0.1071	298	224.3	-441.1	0.75
0.1071	303	231.9	-455.7	0.76
0.1071	308	239.7	-468.8	0.77
0.1071	313	244.3	-464.4	0.78
0.3092	298	225.9	-408.8	0.75
0.5040	298	228.9	-406.0	0.76
0.7010	298	234.2	-417.7	0.78
0.8931	298	238.9	-408.4	0.80

Table 4. Values of parameters of Jones-Dole equation, limiting molar conductance and Walden product of sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at different temperatures

mol % of methanol	Temp. (T) (K)	$(L \text{ mol}^{-1})^{1/2}$	B ($L \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	Λ_m^0 ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)	$\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$ ($\Omega^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ poise}$)
0.1071	298.15	-2.378	5.574	84.01	0.668
0.1071	303.15	-2.431	5.578	91.18	0.702
0.1071	308.15	-2.401	5.583	96.60	0.687
0.1071	313.15	-2.405	5.591	104.81	0.678
0.3092	298.15	-2.392	5.586	88.03	0.635
0.3092	303.15	-2.420	5.595	99.36	0.680
0.3092	308.15	-2.415	5.605	104.13	0.683
0.3092	313.15	-2.419	5.622	109.13	0.684
0.5040	298.15	-2.418	5.804	92.50	0.612
0.5040	303.15	-2.444	5.820	102.94	0.655
0.5040	308.15	-2.432	5.836	110.43	0.677
0.5040	313.15	-2.467	5.852	113.48	0.658
0.7010	298.15	-2.450	5.887	96.70	0.595
0.7010	303.15	-2.452	5.894	108.49	0.640
0.7010	308.15	-2.466	5.914	117.91	0.668
0.7010	313.15	-2.478	5.935	125.04	0.664
0.8931	298.15	-2.505	6.139	104.64	0.604
0.8931	303.15	-2.519	6.150	113.70	0.620
0.8931	308.15	-2.523	6.169	128.48	0.623
0.8931	313.15	-2.550	6.190	132.66	0.648

The B parameter of Jones-Dole equation measures the solute-solvent interactions. The positive values of B -coefficient signify for high solute-solvent interactions¹⁹. The structure maker/breaker behavior of electrolyte in the binary solvent system (DMF + MeOH) is determined by the variation of B -coefficient of Jones-Dole equation with temperature i.e. dB/dT ²⁰. The temperature effect on B -coefficient for sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide shows a positive sign of dB/dT , showing thereby that sodium bromide behaves as structure-breaker in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Conductance studies :

The conductance data has been interpreted with the help of Onsager equation,

$$\Lambda_m = \Lambda_m^0 - K\sqrt{C} \quad (8)$$

where Λ_m^0 is the limiting molar conductance, K is a constant and C is molar concentration. The limiting molar conductance (Λ_m^0) for sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide were obtained by extrapolating the linear plots of Λ_m (Table 2) versus \sqrt{C} to zero concentration (Fig. 2). The limiting

Fig. 2. Plots of λ_m vs $C^{1/2}$ for NaBr in 0.1071 mol percent of methanol in DMF at different temperatures.

molar conductance for sodium bromide in different mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide at 298.15, 303.15, 308.15 and 313.15 K temperatures were recorded in Table 4, shows that limiting molar conductance increases with increase in temperature for a particular concentration, which may be due to increase in ionic mobi-

lity with rise in temperature. Since, in the state of infinite dilution the motion of an ion is limited solely by its interaction with surrounding solvent molecules as there are no other ions within a finite distance. Therefore evaluation of Λ_m^0 should give equally reliable information regarding ion-solvent interactions²¹. Large value of Λ_m^0 may therefore be interpreted as a measure of greater ion-solvent interactions.

The Walden product data ($\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0$) has been given in Table 4. The structure making/breaking nature of electrolyte have been determined from temperature coefficient of Walden product²²; $d(\Lambda_m^0 \eta_0)/dT$. The negative temperature coefficient of Walden product for sodium bromide in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide suggests an increase in the ion-solvent interactions which indicates that sodium bromide behaves as structure-breaker in 0.1070 mol percent of methanol in *N,N*-dimethylformamide.

Conclusion :

Sodium bromide behaves as a structure-breaker in DMF + MeOH system with negative sign of $(\partial^2 \Phi_v^0 / \partial T^2)_p$ and positive sign of dB/dT . The negative temperature coefficient of Walden product supports these results.

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